

Adversity Intelligence and Digital Literacy on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as The Mediating Variable

Fajri Hamdani¹, Dewi Susita², Christian Wiradendi Wolor³

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the effect of adversity intelligence on employee performance, the effect of digital Literacy on employee performance; analyze the effect of adversity intelligence on job satisfaction and digital Literacy on job satisfaction; and analyze the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance, the effect of adversity intelligence on employee performance through mediation job satisfaction and for whether there is an effect of digital Literacy on employee performance through the mediation of job satisfaction at Jakarta State University. The study results show that adversity intelligence influences employee performance at state universities. Digital Literacy influences job satisfaction at state universities. The better the digital Literacy of employees, the higher the job satisfaction of employees. Adversity intelligence affects job satisfaction at state universities. Digital Literacy has no effect on employee performance at state universities; Job Satisfaction positively affects employee performance at state universities, and Adversity Intelligence does not affect Employee Performance through the mediation of Job Satisfaction at state universities. The higher the employee adversity intelligence, the higher the employee performance, which impacts job satisfaction. Digital Literacy affects employee performance by mediating job satisfaction at state universities.

1. Introduction

In the past few years, the whole world has experienced a situation that rarely occurs, namely a pandemic. There have been many changes due to this pandemic that have forced many companies to

¹ State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: fajrihamdani03@gmail.com

² State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: dewisusita_man@unj.ac.id

³ State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. Email : christianwiradendi@unj.ac.id

try to survive. Besides that, many employees have to work using technology and work remotely or from home. Of course, this is a challenge for companies in dividing the workload among employees. On the one hand, employees must also be able to take advantage of these opportunities regarding effectiveness and performance. The obstacles employees face must certainly be in accordance with the institution's or company's goals.

According to Asfan (2020), the number of unemployed, which is increasing daily, is a social problem that requires a solution. The small number of jobs today is the main reason for the increase in the unemployment rate in this country. Someone with adversity intelligence will be able to face obstacles or obstacles that stand in the way of achieving goals. Stoltz (2000), in research of Fauziah (2014), said that the success or failure of a person at work is determined by adversity intelligence, where adversity intelligence can tell how far an individual can endure difficulties and the ability to overcome them, who will be able to overcome difficulties and who will be crushed, who will exceed expectations of their performance and potential and who will fail, who will give up and who will survive. Someone with high emotional intelligence and adversity intelligence will be better able to carry out and complete tasks. The higher a person has both intelligences, the more effective he will be in completing the task. This ability is a very important capital to achieve success in the future. Someone who has emotional intelligence and intelligence, Wardani (2019). This research's state of the art was taken from several examples of previous research as a guide or example for current research. Examples taken are journals analyzing the influence of adversity intelligence to obtain empirical evidence.

One of these journals, entitled "The Impact of adversity intelligence and work commitment on cyberloafing behavior," was authored by T Rahayuningsih and Putra (2018) and aims to determine the effect of adversity intelligence and work commitment on lecturer cyberloafing behavior in the era of the Asean Economic Community (AEC). This research is useful for the development of industrial theory and organizational psychology regarding work behavior, as well as suggestions for maintaining factors that make lecturers avoid unproductive work habits that are cyberloafing. One way to outline so many publications is by how to do a bibliometric study. According to Waaijer and Palmblad in research (2019), Ar-Raheem (2019) describes that each publication metadata consists of data on the title, author, abstract, keywords, references, the journal where the paper was published, the country of each author, the institution where each author works, and many other data. Bibliometric studies are usually used to evaluate the performance of universities, research institutes, or researchers. However, this study can also be used to understand how a field of knowledge is structured or how research develops on certain topics.

The COVID-19 outbreak has opened up a new scenario where teachers must have sufficient digital literacy to teach online and apply current and innovative educational service models to measure their digital skills. According to Italian researchers, in research by Shopova (2014), the computer has become an instrument of the alphabet "by which one reads about the world" in the form of words and pages. In this way, computers and the internet brought people back to using written communication. The development of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and their integration in all areas of people's lives and work provides for the first time the possibility of instant and unrestricted access to a wide range of information that is continuously being enriched, changed and updated. This new model of society requires citizens with the necessary skills and competencies to take advantage of the potential of new technologies and take an active role in economic, social, and cultural life.

It is the same with UNJ, which requires support in the administrative field that can facilitate the implementation of the educational process properly. After becoming a BLU, UNJ had bureaucratic

instruments consisting of the General Affairs and Civil Service Bureau (BUK), the Bureau of Academic Administration, Student Affairs and Public Relations (BAKHUM), and the Bureau of Finance (BK).

The quality of administrative staff resources is an important concern for UNJ to continue to improve, especially through training related to task competencies and those related to the civil servant bureaucracy promotion hierarchy. In addition to training, efforts to improve the quality of administrative staff are also carried out by supporting administrative staff to continue their formal education to a higher level, both undergraduate and postgraduate.

Administrative management is carried out to facilitate organizing education and organization at UNJ. The principle of speed and accuracy underlies the service efforts carried out by the general administration.

Table1. Recapitulation of the Number of Non-PNS Education Personnel by Work Unit

No	Work unit	Number of Employees
1	Chancellor's Secretariat	6
2	Bureau of Academic, Student Affairs, and Public Relations	19
3	Financial Bureau	19
4	General Affairs and Personnel Bureau	108
5	Endura	6
6	faculty of Language and Art	30
7	faculty of Economics	18
8	faculty of Sport Science	40
9	Faculty of Sports Science	1
10	faculty of Science Education	50
11	Faculty of Social Science	22
12	Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences	23
13	Faculty of Psychology Education	7
14	Faculty of Engineering	43
15	Research institutions and community service	11
16	Institute for Educational Development and Quality Assurance	19
17	P1 Professional Certification Institute (LPP1)	2
18	Postgraduate	30
19	Internal Oversight Unit	1
20	UPT. Language	4
21	UPT. Library	9
22	UPT. Information and communication technology	10
Total		478

According to Nawaz and Kundi (2010), The necessity of digital Literacy is evident from the findings and arguments of some researchers. For example, ICT (connectivity tool) helps reduce the problem of 'isolation' and 'disempowerment' for developing countries and marginalized groups. The Digital Opportunities Initiative (DOI) is a powerful tool for 'poverty alleviation' and 'economic development' in developing countries. Developing countries like Pakistan are entering into 'international and national' partnerships to leverage global ICT resources. Moreover, in a university setting, e-Learning tools create a 'leaner' and 'collaborative learning environment' in which they are empowered to control their learning process.

In doing a job, an employee should have high performance, but this is difficult to achieve, often even employees who have decreased performance, even though they have a lot of work experience, still lack motivation both from within themselves and from outside factors; institutions have also conducted a lot of training to increase the motivation of its human resources, which in this case are the employees. In their statement, Sánchez-Cruzado et al. (2021) spoke that digital Literacy is also included in the current Spanish legislation, in the Organic Law 8/2013 of December 9, to improve the quality of education as another competency that must be performed, equivalent to mathematical and scientific, linguistic, social, or artistic competencies. Based on this consideration, educators and teachers must know how to use ICT instrumentally and an integrated methodological model in teaching-learning. Educators and teachers must work on the capabilities and uses of technology for learning and knowledge (TAC) that will progressively shape their digital Literacy.

The learning environment is the most basic feature that distinguishes distance education from face-to-face education. Differences in the learning environment certainly affect the skills used by individuals. The scope of skills used in the learning process develops or emerges from a new concept. In this respect, digital Literacy can be expressed as an increasingly important skill integrated into the new generation of learning environments.

Since changing its function to become a university, UNJ has changed government regulations and policies regarding higher education (Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System). is "Become a reputable university in the Asian region." Because of that, UNJ needs to anticipate the development of its achievements in the international spectrum, not only in terms of educators but also educational staff who have good digital Literacy and can turn obstacles into success in achieving goals.

Researchers conducted interviews with related officials and representatives of Jakarta State University employees that apart from a lack of communication on the job, in improving the performance of UNJ employees, it is also very necessary for employees who can solve a problem by preparing alternative solutions quickly and employees with good digital Literacy are needed to support today's work. This is also supported by the results of an internal survey conducted by researchers on educational staff by distributing surveys to 25 (twenty-five) respondents that the factors affecting the performance of UNJ employees get a percentage of more than 90% (ninety percent).

Table 2. Recapitulation of 2022 Internal Survey Results

Variable	Statement	Answer Percentage	
		Yes	No

Digital Literacy	I can search for and access data, information, and content on digital media as needed	96%	4%
Motivation	I feel the current job is in accordance with what I expected	60%	40%
Adversity Intelligence	The more problems I face, the more excited I am to solve them	92%	8%
Responsibility for work	The tasks that become my job are in accordance with the skills that I have	68%	32%
Training	The training I received was very useful in improving my abilities and skills	88%	12%
Satisfaction	Attention and appreciation are important factors in work	88%	12%
Loyalty	Awards can improve my work performance	88%	12%

(Source: Data processed by researchers - 2022)

Another problem that must be faced is that not all employees desire to continue honing their skills. Maybe that is what UNJ needs to consider to continue to require programs such as character building and periodic ability test training.

The imperative for digital Literacy was magnified by events in recent years that have called for greater technological competence, critical and ethical thinking, and a sense of digital citizenship. From foreign state-backed hacks, fake news campaigns (and alternative facts) to corporate data breaches to national migrations to online learning due to the global health crisis that requires greater focus and dedication to digital literacy development than we currently do (Tham et al., 2021).

In other words, UNJ needs to seriously identify various problems related to the decline in standards related to the quality of the university's teaching staff, especially those directly related to the fulfillment of superior qualifications for all standards as well as the competence and qualifications of educational staff which greatly support the success of achieving the vision, mission, and college goals. Reinforced by statements of Kazmi & Javaid (2022) state that a company will make a lot of efforts to meet the needs of employees and ensure productivity and conductivity in the workplace. Employees are considered a tangible business asset that drives the day-to-day operating activities of an organization or agency.

Based on the data gap above and the results of the bibliometric analysis using the Vosviewers application, which has been described by the author above, the purpose of writing this article is to determine the Effect of Adversity Intelligence and Digital Literacy on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as a Variable.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, the subject was employees/teaching staff at the State University of Jakarta (UNJ), and the research time started from the thesis seminar to the completion of the thesis. This study focuses on the variable Adversity Intelligence and Digital Literacy on employee performance, with performance satisfaction as a mediating variable. This research is also quantitative research conducted by collecting data using research instruments on certain populations or samples. The data analysis carried out was quantitative or statistical, intending to test the hypotheses that had been set (Usman et al. (2008). The data sources used in this study consisted of primary and secondary sources.

Furthermore, when viewed from the point of view of data collection methods or techniques, data collection techniques can be carried out using questionnaires. Observation and literature study. Data collection aims to obtain data related to research.

3. Results and Discussions

Adversity Intelligence on employee performance

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient) shows the original sample value of 0.177 on adversity intelligence on employee performance. This means that there is a positive influence on the adversity intelligence variable on employee performance variables. In addition, it also shows a t-statistic value of 2.108 and a p-value of 0.035 <0.05, which means that adversity intelligence has a significant direct effect on employee performance. This research is in line with the theory carried out by Diyah Arfidianingrum et al. (2013), explaining that someone with a high endurance dimension will be optimistic, not easily discouraged, and continue to try to solve any problems and difficulties that arise. Related to the work-family conflict they experienced. Vice versa. So it can be said that adversity intelligence is one part of the individual factors that can influence the occurrence of work-family conflict experienced by mothers who work as nurses because adversity intelligence is the ability to respond appropriately to any existing difficulties or problems. This hypothesis is strengthened by the descriptive results on the adversity intelligence variable showing that most respondents answered neutral with an average of 4.42.

In contrast, on average, employee performance strongly agreed, namely 4.23. Most of the respondents feel that in order to get maximum performance and employees must be able to control themselves when there are individual difficulties. Vice versa, if individual difficulties are not controlled, then the performance will not be optimal.

It is similar to the research conducted by Azahra and Isa (2021), namely, the adversity quotient has a positive and significant effect on performance. In line with what was discussed by Sok (2022) in his research, one of a company's successes is realized through achieving the vision and mission, and goals. One aspect that spearheads the success of the company is employee performance. Good or bad performance can be influenced by internal factors, namely the adversity quotient, and external factors, namely the quality of work life.

Digital Literacy on job satisfaction

Based on a statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient) shows the original sample value of 0.219 on digital Literacy on job satisfaction. This means that digital literacy variables have a positive influence on job satisfaction variables. In addition, it also shows a t statistical value of 2,187 and a p-value of 0,029 <0.05, which means that digital Literacy has a direct significant effect on job satisfaction. This study's results align with the theory put forward by Rahman et al. (2021). Digital

Literacy is an important requirement for every individual to survive in a digital society. Initiatives have been underway to develop comprehensive digital literacy frameworks in many countries. The initiative goes by different names for frameworks, including digital Literacy, digital competence, digital readiness, and digital intelligence. This paper argues that the use of a different name and the inclusion of new elements in the development of a digital literacy framework demonstrate dynamic and progressive efforts in developing a more comprehensive and adaptive framework to face the challenges of the industrial revolution 4.0.

The hypothesis is strengthened by the descriptive results on the digital literacy variable showing that the majority of respondents answered agree with the highest average of 4.55, and on the job satisfaction variable, they answered strongly agree with the highest average of 3.98. the higher the ability to operate digital technology, it will have an impact on job satisfaction as measured by the indicator of the amount of salary earned.

It has results that are in accordance with research conducted by Nusannas et al. (2020). The greater a person's self-confidence in his ability to succeed in doing his job is job satisfaction and individual confidence in his ability to face new challenges research conducted by Basir et al. (2021) Discussion of data concludes that world universities believe that digital technology which is increasingly trending can be learning innovation even though the world will continue to hit the world of education. Therefore, the researchers hope that these findings should support other studies in the future.

Adversity Intelligence on job satisfaction

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient) shows the original sample value of 0.273 on adversity intelligence on job satisfaction. This means there is a positive influence on the adversity intelligence variable on job satisfaction variables. In addition, it also shows a t-statistic value of 2,925 and a p-value of 0,003 <0.05, which means that adversity intelligence has a direct significant effect on job satisfaction. Therefore, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted.

This research aligns with the theory put forward by Shen (2014) that employees with high adversity intelligence are valuable talents for the company. High job satisfaction is a sign that the organization is well-managed and results from effective behavior management. A high adversity quotient in an employee will reflect the individual's sense of belonging to the organization so that what he does can cause a feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with Simbolon (2013).

The hypothesis is strengthened by the descriptive results on the adversity intelligence variable and job satisfaction showing that most respondents answered neutrally on the adversity intelligence variable with an average of 4.42, while for job satisfaction, the job satisfaction variable answered strongly agreed with the highest average of 3.98. the higher the ability to control oneself in solving problems, the more job satisfaction in receiving the amount of salary that is obtained is in accordance with the performance carried out. It is in accordance with research conducted by Sudiro (2018), Mirza, and Adrizka (2018), which state a positive correlation between AQ and job satisfaction.

Digital Literacy on employee performance

Based on a statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient) shows the original sample value of 0.130 on digital Literacy on employee performance. This means there is a positive influence on the digital literacy variable on employee performance variables. In addition, it also shows a t-statistic value of 0.973 and a p-value of 0.331 > 0.05, which means that digital Literacy has no direct significant effect on employee performance.

The results of this study are not in line with the theory put forward by Farias and Gaytan et al. (2022), who said in their research that digital Literacy emerged simultaneously with the evolution of the internet and demands knowledge of how to access, search, and critically analyze information. With digital knowledge and development for employees, it will make it easier for employees to complete their work.

The hypothesis is strengthened by the descriptive results on the digital literacy variable digital literacy shows that the majority of respondents agreed with the highest average of 4.55, and the average employee performance chose to strongly agree namely 4.23. the higher the employee's expertise in using digital search engines, the more serious the employee is in carrying out the work in order to get maximum results. It is in contrast to research conducted by Kamal et al. (2021) and Santoso et al. (2019). Their research results obtained a significant effect of digital Literacy on supervisory performance. While a growing literature indicates that employee digital skills are important for enabling individuals and organizations to take advantage of digital workspaces, there is an empirical understanding of their effect on performance. The role of digital Literacy needs to be developed according to performance developments because digital Literacy is a person's ability to understand and use information in various formats originating from various digital sources displayed via a computer in carrying out tasks and helping to improve the quality of work. The difference between this research and previous research is in the object of research; in the previous research, it was done on supervisory performance, while in this research, it was done on employee performance.

Job Satisfaction on employee performance

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient) shows the original sample value of 0.409 on job satisfaction and employee performance. This means that there is a positive influence on the variable of job satisfaction on employee performance variables. In addition, it also shows a t-statistic value of 3,478 and a p-value of 0,001 <0.05, which means that job satisfaction has a direct significant effect on employee performance.

This study's results align with the theory put forward by Bagaskara and Rahardja (2018) that increasing employee job satisfaction will further improve employee performance. Likewise, the research conducted by Jufrien & Intan (2021) also shows that the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance is positive and significantly influences the value of job satisfaction on employee performance.

This hypothesis is strengthened by descriptive results on job satisfaction and employee performance variables showing that most respondents answered strongly agree with the highest average of 3.98 and 4.23 on employee performance. Respondents in this study showed that the salary scale received by employees was not appropriate, while employees were always serious about carrying out their work. It is similar the research conducted by Rahmawati and Syahril (2021). The results obtained from their research are that work motivation and job satisfaction have a significant positive effect partially or simultaneously on the performance of employees of PT. Sinar Mas Medan.

Adversity Intelligence on Employee Performance through the Mediation of Job Satisfaction

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient), the adversity intelligence variable influences employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation that acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.112, which means that there is a positive influence in the influence of adversity intelligence on

employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 1.826, and the p-value is $0.068 > 0.05$, which means that the adversity intelligence variable has an indirect significant effect on employee performance, with job satisfaction acting as a mediator. Therefore,

This is in line with the theory carried out by Setyaji et al. (2020) in their research, which explains that this can happen because individuals tend to concentrate more fully on their problems and are reluctant to leave the problem before finding a solution. Job satisfaction as a mediator in improving employee performance is a feeling condition arising from the perception that work increases material and psychological needs, Loan (2020). According to Saputra and Andani (2021), in their research, it explains that companies do many things to fulfill employees' wishes to increase their productivity and maintain employee job satisfaction. Satisfied employees will work without a burden and give more effort to their work, loyalty to the company and its leadership. Companies can pay less attention to the needs and desires of their employees so that job satisfaction decreases.

The hypothesis is strengthened by the descriptive results on adversity intelligence, employee performance, and job satisfaction showing that the majority of respondents answered strongly agree, agree, and neutral on these three variables with the highest average value of respondents' answers, 4.42 adversity intelligence variable, employee performance variable 4.23, and 3.98 on variable job satisfaction. Respondents in this study perceive that responsibility for employee decision-making must be completed in earnest to get maximum results.

This research has results that are not following previous studies that have been studied by several researchers, including (Wardani, 2019), who stated in their research that through the social inquiry model, adversity intelligence and emotional intelligence will play an effective role in improving social skills. It can be concluded that adversity and emotional intelligence through social inquiry models on social skills. There are differences in the variables and research objects in this study, so the results are not following previous studies. This job satisfaction cannot mediate the effect of adversity intelligence on employee performance.

Digital Literacy on employee performance through the Mediation of job satisfaction

Based on a statistical analysis of the path coefficient (path coefficient), the digital literacy variable influences employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation that acts as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of these three variables is 0.089, which means there is a positive influence in the influence of digital Literacy on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 2.063, and the p-value is $0.039 > 0.05$, which means that the digital literacy variable has a significant indirect effect on employee performance, with job satisfaction acting as a mediator.

This study's results align with the theory put forward by Audrin and Audrin (2022). With the rise of digitalization over the last few decades, digital Literacy has taken a central role in our society and has become an important concern for institutions and policymakers. Institutions and individuals to identify, adapt and adopt progress to their contextual needs. Job satisfaction as a mediator in improving employee performance is that companies do many things to fulfill employees' wishes to increase their productivity and maintain employee job satisfaction (Saputra and Andani, 2021).

The hypothesis is strengthened by descriptive results on digital Literacy, employee performance, and job satisfaction showing that the majority of respondents answered strongly agree and agree on these three variables, with the highest average value of respondents' answers 4.55 on digital literacy variables, 4.23 on employee performance variables and 3.98 on job satisfaction variables. Respondents in this study have the perception that using digitalization makes work easier and faster and faster so they can maximize work results.

This research is in accordance with Abbas et al. (2019) which concluded that digital Literacy significantly affects students' communication skills, research skills, and self-confidence, while digital Literacy has an insignificant effect on students' CGPA. And research conducted by Masharyono et al. (2020). The results of his research show that Employee Engagement and Ability have a positive and significant effect on employee performance which is mediated by digital Literacy.

4. Conclusions

This research concludes several statements as follows. First, adversity intelligence affects the performance of employees at state universities. The better the employee adversity intelligence, the better the performance. Second, digital Literacy influences job satisfaction at state universities. The better the digital Literacy of employees, the higher employee job satisfaction. Third, adversity intelligence affects job satisfaction at state universities. The higher the adversity intelligence possessed by employees, the higher employee job satisfaction. Forth, digital literacy has no effect on employee performance at state universities. The higher the employee's digital Literacy, the lower the employee's performance.

Fifth, Job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance at state universities. The higher the employee job satisfaction, the better the employee performance. Sixth, Adversity Intelligence does not affect Employee Performance by mediating Job Satisfaction at public universities. The higher the employee adversity intelligence, the higher the employee performance, which impacts job satisfaction. Seventh, digital literacy influences employee performance by mediating job satisfaction at state universities. The higher the digital Literacy of employees, the lower the employee's performance which impacts job satisfaction.

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